

Complex Compounds of Iridium. Part IV.

BY PRAFULLA CHANDRA RÂY AND NRIPENDRA NATH GHOSH.

The action of ammonia on $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (yellow variety) at 140° and the consequent formation of $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot 2\text{NH}_3$ and $(\text{IrCl}_5\text{NH}_3)\text{Cl}_2$ have already been described (Rây and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 517). The mother liquor from these Ir-ammines on concentration over sulphuric acid in vacuum and subsequent treatment with alcohol, gave extremely hygroscopic precipitate which could not be further examined. Attempts to prepare the corresponding nitrate by treating the mother liquor with silver nitrate solution, led to no better results. On the other hand, treatment with hot silver sulphate solution resulted in the isolation of a sulphate of the formula $(\text{Ir} \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot 5\text{NH}_3)_2 (\text{SO}_4)_3, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The sulphate radicals were found to be ionisable and completely precipitable by barium chloride. Determination of molecular conductivity gave, however, abnormally high values due probably to partial hydrolysis. From the formation of the above sulphate, it may be concluded that the mother liquor of the ammines, contains a chloride having the formula $(\text{Ir} \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot 5\text{NH}_3)\text{Cl}_3$.

But the action of ammonia on $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (yellow variety) simply at the temperature of the water-bath produced a new Ir-ammine $(\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot \text{NH}_3)$ —only one Et_2S being replaced by ammonia—along with a small amount of the products formed at higher temperatures (*cf.* Rây and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*).

By the action of ethyl sulphide on ammonium chloroiridate, three compounds (A) $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (yellow), (B) $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 2 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (red) and (C) $\text{Ir}_2\text{Cl}_5 \cdot 4\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, have been obtained, of which (A) and (B) have been described to be geometrical isomers (Rây and co-workers, *ibid.*, 1932, 9, 251; 1933, 10, 275). The red crystals of the compound (B) freshly isolated from chloroform has been found to contain one molecule of chloroform of crystallisation which it gives up spontaneously at the ordinary temperature and in course of a quarter of an hour, becomes reddish-white and opaque like an efflorescent compound. The reddish white mass has been found, on analysis, to correspond with the compound (B). The melting points of the red crystals and the

reddish white mass are identical due evidently to the rapid and spontaneous loss of the chloroform of crystallisation. Although the chloroform of crystallisation is present in several organic compounds, *e.g.*, the condensation product of leuconic acid with tolylene diamine chloroform being expelled at 140° (*Ber.*, 1886, 19, 776), methyl-ethyl-allylphenylammonium iodide (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3795), etc., its presence is rather rare with inorganic and organometallic compounds. It should, however, be pointed out that during crystallisation of the compound (B) from chloroform, a small fraction is always transformed into (A), *i.e.*, the yellow variety.

The action of bases on the compound (B) will form the subject of our next communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of $(\text{Ir}\cdot\text{Et}_2\text{S}\cdot 5\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{SO}_4)_3, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.— $\text{IrCl}_3\cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (2.5 g.) was heated in a sealed tube with liquor ammonia (18 c.c.) first on a water-bath for three hours and finally in the bomb-furnace at 130° - 140° for 3 hours. Ethyl sulphide replaced by ammonia was extracted with ether. From the main solution $\text{IrCl}_3\cdot\text{Et}_2\text{S}\cdot 2\text{NH}_3$ and $(\text{IrCl}\cdot 5\text{NH}_3)\text{Cl}_2$ were obtained and a viscous liquid remained, which was not crystallisable and was treated with hot solution of silver sulphate till complete precipitation was effected. Silver chloride, thus precipitated, was removed by filtration. The filtrate decomposes at the temperature of water-bath and was hence concentrated in vacuum over sulphuric acid. The concentrated solution, thus obtained, was treated with alcohol in order to precipitate the compound. The process of precipitation was repeated thrice by dissolving the precipitate in the least possible quantity of water each time, and the compound was finally crystallised from moist acetone. It is hygroscopic and contains two molecules of water of crystallisation. [Found: N, 12.98, 13.12; S, 13.8; Ir, 36.93, 35.81. $(\text{Ir}\cdot\text{Et}_2\text{S}\cdot 5\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{SO}_4)_3, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 13.21; S, 15.09; Ir, 36.41 per cent].

Determination of Ionisable Sulphate of $(\text{Ir}\cdot\text{Et}_2\text{S}\cdot 5\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{SO}_4)_3, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

(i) *Precipitation method.*—A certain amount of the above substance was treated with cold barium chloride solution. Barium sulphate was precipitated. [Found: SO_4'' , 26.63. $(\text{Ir}\cdot\text{Et}_2\text{S}\cdot 5\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{SO}_4)_3, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires (if three SO_4'' be ionisable) SO_4'' , 27.17 per cent].

(ii) *Molecular conductivity Measurement.*

Mol. conc. (M)	0.01	0.005	0.0025	0.00125	0.000625	0.000312
Mol. conductivity.	322	364	408	466	532	585

(Molecular conductivity of aluminium sulphate at infinite dilution is 373).

Preparation of $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot \text{NH}_3$.— $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (3 g.) (yellow variety) was heated on a water-bath in a sealed tube with liquor ammonia (18 c.c.) with occasional shaking, till all the $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ went into solution. About 20 hours' heating was required. When cold, an orange-yellow crystalline substance and a yellow solution with a layer of ethyl sulphide floating over it, were obtained. The orange-yellow crystalline substance was isolated and recrystallised from hot water, m.p. 155° . (Found: Cl, 21.1; S, 12.92; Ir, 38.95, 39.0. $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot \text{NH}_3$ requires Cl, 21.45; S, 12.88, Ir, 38.87 per cent). From the main solution, other Ir-ammines were obtained.

Preparation of $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, CHCl_3 —Ethyl sulphide (5 c.c.) was added to ammonium chloriridate (5 g.) in water (300 c.c.) and alcohol (30 c.c.) and it was heated on a water bath (80°) for 12 hours, when a substance gradually separated out, the colour of the solution changing from deep red to yellowish red. The substance, thus separated, was isolated and extracted repeatedly with hot benzene in order to remove $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (yellow variety); a residue remained, which on treatment with chloroform, gave a deep red solution from which red transparent crystals were obtained. These crystals turned on reddish-white opaque mass within a quarter of an hour, m.p. 171° . (Found: Cl, 31.1; S, 13.67, 14.0; Ir, 28.0, 28.1. $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, CHCl_3 requires Cl, 30.9; S, 13.9; Ir, 28.0 per cent).